

Mitigating Risks from Legacy Uranium Mining Sites in Central Asia: environmental policy analysis

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Executive Summary

This policy analysis recommends adoption of a risk-based international environmental policy to mitigate abandoned uranium mining that pose the highest health and environmental risk to communities, livelihoods, and economies in former Soviet Central Asia. An alternative policy for *all* sites in Central Asia (if sufficient funding is made available) is also discussed. Following the disintegration of the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics (USSR) in 1991, the Soviet republics of Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan were made independent. These Central Asian republics were for decades used by the USSR for uranium mining to support weapons and other state programs (Egorov, N., et al., 2014). The collapse resulted in the abandonment of mining sites without proper closure or risk mitigation; today, 26 years later, local communities face radiation exposure through air, soil, water and food (Chen, S.B., et al., 2005). Other (secondary) threats also caused by former mining are slope failure (landslides), subsidence (i.e., sinkhole formation), mudflows, and flooding (Egorov, N., et al., 2014; Eisenbud, M. and Gesell, T.F., 1997; Lind, O.C., et al., 2013; Hamby, D.M. and Tynybekov, A.K., 2002; Honkonen, T., 2013; International Atomic Energy Agency, 2016; Priest, N.D., et al., 2013; Salbu, B., 2013; Stegnar, P., et al., 2013; Trnqvist, R., et al., 2011). A summary of existing (and accessible) policy on the regulation of uranium mining for the Republic of Kyrgyzstan (relatively open state), developed by Tuula Honkonen, L.L.M. (University of East Finland) was reviewed to infer regional mining policy. Under regional law, legacy (abandoned) mining sites have no owner, so no one to hold accountable for mine site closure or risk mitigation. Effectively the state becomes the owner of last resort – an owner with limited financial means and/or political motivation to mitigate the risks. Complicating the situation is the transboundary nature of the Central Asian republics, with transport of radiation contamination from one state to a neighboring state a real risk. To address the risks, three international policy alternatives (to be implemented by an international agency such as the United Nations or the International Atomic Energy Agency) were considered in this analysis: Alternative 1 - baseline (*status quo*); Alternative 2 – ‘Risk-based’ mitigation; and Alternative 3 – ‘All Sites’ mitigation. Local preferences and values were incorporated into the analysis using *weighting factors*. The weighting factors were estimated based on the author’s experience working with local communities in Central Asia.

1. Background and Purpose

Abandoned uranium mining sites (Legacy sites) are located throughout the former Union of Soviet Socialist Republics (USSR) Republics (located in Central Asia) (i.e., Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan). Many of these abandoned mining sites present continuing threats to the lives and livelihoods of stakeholders - local populations and neighboring communities – both in-country and across international borders (Yuldashev, B.S., et al., 2005). Radiation exposure through air, soil, water and food (Chen, S.B., et al., 2005) are the primary health risk to populations; other (secondary) threats

also caused by former mining are slope failure (landslides), subsidence (i.e., sinkhole formation), mudflows, and flooding (Egorov, N., et al., 2014; Eisenbud, M. and Gesell, T.F., 1997; Lind, O.C., et al., 2013; Hamby, D.M. and Tynybekov, A.K., 2002; Honkonen, T., 2013; International Atomic Energy Agency, 2016; Priest, N.D., et al., 2013; Salbu, B., 2013; Stegnar, P., et al., 2013; Trnqvist, R., et al., 2011).

Further complicating the situation are the following circumstances:

1. The absence of country-specific environmental policy, strong institutions, technical capacity - and financial programs - to mitigate the Legacy sites (Honkonen, T., 2013)
2. Central Asia is characterized as international transboundary (i.e., several mountainous counties clustered closely together, sharing critical surface and groundwater water resources and agricultural areas)

Tuula Honkonen, L.L.M. of the University of East Finland reviewed post-Soviet policy on uranium mining for the Republic of Kyrgyzstan and found an absence of policy directing closure and/or mitigation of legacy mining sites (i.e., those sites which were abandoned following the collapse of the USSR) (Honkonen, T., 2013).

To protect populations, livelihoods, and minimize cross-border conflicts from contamination transport and/or disaster threats in Central Asia, a legacy mine site closure and mitigation policy (with sufficient funding) at an international level is immediately needed.

1. Policy alternatives and evaluation criteria

The following environmental policy alternatives to clean up the are considered:

- Alternative 1 - No Change (*status quo*)
- Alternative 2 - Risk-based, highest priority sites only
- Alternative 3 - All Legacy sites

A 'No Change' alternative is considered as a baseline for comparison with the other proposed alternatives and represents *status quo*. Next, the 'Risk-based' alternative is based on a logical ordering of Legacy sites based on potential risks to the health to the population; it produces a priority ranking of sites. This approach considers optimal use of limited funds to clean up and manage the highest priority sites first. For the third alternative, all Legacy sites are cleaned up.

To analyze the three proposed alternatives, the following eight evaluation criteria will be considered. The analysis of each evaluation criterion is constrained by requiring it be minimized or maximized, as shown following each criterion in (parenthesizes). As an example, considering evaluation criterion number one, a proposed environmental policy should (minimize) the human health risks to the affected population. Health risks could be increased during, for example, earth moving operations to stabilize a legacy mine tailings (waste rock) pile, causing dust (laden with radioactive particles) which can subsequently be inhaled by near-by population (International Atomic Energy Agency, 2010?; International Atomic Energy Agency, 2015; International Atomic Energy Agency, 2016).

- 1) Human health risks (goal = minimize)
- 2) Livelihood disruption (goal = minimize)
- 3) Population displacement (goal = minimize)

- 4) Radionuclide transport risk (goal = minimize)
- 5) Food supply radiation dose risk (goal = minimize)
- 6) Land stability risks (goal = minimize)
- 7) Transboundary conflicts (goal = minimize)
- 8) Cost (goal = minimize)

Decision analysis weighting will be assigned based on perceived preferences of the local/regional population, as practicable.

2. Policy analytical analysis

The three proposed policy alternatives were assessed using an impact assessment (*ex ante*) analysis. The analysis is shown in Table 1. Policy Alternatives Analysis.

Explanation of the inputs to Table 1. Policy Alternatives Analysis:

Weighting Factors – To incorporate opinion and values of the affected population, a weighting factor was introduced to the analysis matrix. **The weighting factor is a numeric value between 0 and 1 (0 being least desirable, 1 being most desirable)** and is the average response about each criterion collected from a representative portion of the affected population. For this analysis, since focus groups, community meetings, and polls were not possible due to the geographic isolated location of the area, weighting factors were estimated based on personal experience working with local populations in Central Asia.

Goal – Each evaluation criterion is constrained by requiring it to be either minimized or maximized. **For this analysis all evaluation criteria are required to be minimized.**

Criterion Score – Criterion scoring is based on how well a criterion fulfils a specified *goal* for that criterion. For example, for Alternative Number 1 – No Change (*status quo*) scores 0 (the lowest score possible) for minimizing impacts to human health, since the *status quo* alternative does nothing to change the ongoing environmental exposures, for example from radioactive tailing piles seeping into surface water resources used for irrigation and/or a source of potable water. **Scores are expressed as a number between 0 and 1 (0 being least effective, 1 being most effective).**

Alternatives were analyzed in Table 1. as follows: *Criterion Score x Weighting Factor* for each Evaluation Criterion produced a sub-score (for each criterion). To derive a total score for each policy alternative, all sub-scores were added (for all criterion) to produce an Overall Score for each policy alternative.

The overall scores were (from Table.1) were:

<u>Alternative</u>	<u>Overall Score</u>
Alternative 1	2.7
Alternative 2	3.9
Alternative 3	4.1

This analysis allowed insight, enhanced understanding of the complexities underlying the three policy alternatives and eight measurement criteria, and facilitated comparison of the alternatives.

3. Policy stakeholders

Probable stakeholders are identified in Table 2.

In general, all stakeholders would like cleanup of Legacy sites. However, depending on the policy alternative selected support varies among the stakeholders. Specifically, for Alternative 2 (Risk based cleanup), those residents, businesses, water, and agriculture cooperative groups not located in a high risk area, and therefore will not have local conditions remediated, are much less supportive of Alternative 2. In addition, governmental organizations located in areas not to be remediated are also less supportive since other jurisdictions may benefit from cleanup and they do not. For Alternative 3 (All Sites cleanup) some government representatives, and representatives from water and agricultural groups expressed concerns that obtaining adequate funding for an All Sites alternative may take too long, prolonging suffering of those effected the most.

4. Policy implementation trade-offs

The following general trade-offs may be encountered depending on the Alternative selected.

Both policy Alternatives 2 and 3 have the potential to disrupt livelihoods and displace population (depending on site-specific circumstances), negative tradeoffs to fulfil the environmental mitigation. Specifically, Alternative 2 has these potential negative impacts but restricted to those areas that have the highest human health risk. Alternative 3 (All Sites), however, may result in these tradeoffs being much more widespread across the region.

In addition, livelihood disruption implies economic disruption. The extent of any resulting economic disruption is dependent upon site-specific circumstances, e.g., specific livelihoods and industries effected by mitigation activities (Raiser, M. and Dobronogov, A., 2006).

5. Policy possible unintended consequences

Table 3 lists possible unintended consequences associated with Alternatives 2 and 3. Community displacement and forced livelihood changes (negative consequences) are possible as mitigation action occur. The extent of these changes will depended on location-specific circumstances. Also associated with Alternatives 2 and 3 are increased radiation dose and increased environmental damage during mitigation actions. For example, excavation and removal of radioactive waste piles may require a temporary increase in the risks of exposure to radioactive substances (to workers and near-by population). Lastly, positive consequences may occur from the implementation of Alternatives 2 and 3 – reduction in geologic hazards (for example slope instability corrected during land reclamation activities) and flood control (for example, drainage modification/correction coincident with land reclamation activities).

6. Recommendations and conclusions

Policy Alternatives 2 and 3 both fulfil the goal of mitigating threats from abandoned uranium mines in Central Asia. A comparative analysis of Alternatives 2 and 3 (with Alternative 1 – *status quo* as a baseline) showed the two alternatives were both perceived by stakeholders as beneficial solutions, but with Alternative 3 scoring slightly higher (Alternative 3, score = 4.1 versus Alternative 2, score = 3.9)

(see Table 1. Policy Alternatives Analysis).

Despite the numerical results of the Policy Alternatives Analysis the political reality of successful international policy development and effective implementation is focused on obtaining sufficient funding. Because of this reality, this analyst recommends immediate adoption of Alternative 2, with later adoption of Alternative 3 (should additional funding be made available).

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Tables

Table 1. Policy alternatives analysis

Table 2. Stakeholders

Table 3. Potential unintended consequences

Table 1. Policy Alternatives Analysis

		Evaluation Criteria, weighting, (maximize or minimize)							Overall Score
Weighting Goal	Human health risk	Livelihood disruption	Population displacement	Radionuclide transport risk	Food radiation dose risk	Land Stability	Trans - boundary conflicts	Cost	
		1.0 (min)	0.9 (min)	0.9 (min)	0.7 (min)	0.9 (min)	0.8 (min)	0.7 (min)	
Policy Alternatives (3)	Criterion Scoring								
1 – No change (Status quo)	0.0	1.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	2.7
2 – Risk-based regulations and remediation	1.0	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	3.9
3 – All legacy sites remediated	1.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.0	4.1

weighting = local population preference (estimated) of goal importance (local value and preference factor; 1 is maximum, 0 is minimum)

Costs = costs incurred for investigation and remediation of contaminated sites

 = on a scale of 0.0, 0.5, or 1.0 (1.0 being most likely to achieve the policy goal), how likely is alternative to achieve goal

 = calculated score for each policy alternative. Likelihood x Weighting for each Evaluation Criterion, then summed across all criterion categories to produce the alternative's score

Table 2. Stakeholders

Residents	Businesses	Farmers	Non-Governmental Organizations	Water Supply Groups and Districts
Consumers	Municipalities, States	Fishing Groups and Individuals	International Atomic Energy Agency	Agricultural Groups and Districts

Table 3. Potential unintended consequences

Community displacement	Increased radiation dose	Reduction in geologic hazards
Forced livelihood changes	Increased environmental damage	Flood control